

Factors Affecting Employability of Persons with Disabilities

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Abstract—This delved into the factors like skills, educational attainment, age and sex of Persons with Disabilities (PWD's) that may affect hiring preferences of private and public sectors. Theories on Skills Approached of Robert Katz and Kurt Fischer and Zheng Yan's on dynamic skills that recognizes cognitive abilities as necessary qualification for a disabled person are basis of the study. A total of ten skills that a PWD must develop, preferred formal education and disabilities that employers may still consider employable through the Human Resource Officers, Managers and Supervisors of private and public agencies were analysed. Discrimination exist despite presence of Local Laws in conjunction with International Laws on PWD's particularly on age and the kind of disability. Communication and teamwork, ability to analyse and practical computer applications are required soft and hard skills respectively.

Keywords— Soft skills, hard skills, factors affecting employment of PWD's, problems of workforce.

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of globalization open a wider possibility for person with disability to interact with others in the workplace. Many institutions in the Philippines are compliant to local laws in employing physically handicapped people. Luxurious hotels in Europe, a garment factory in India, a footwear manufacturing in America amongst others who hire persons with disabilities (PWD's). Noe Hollenbeck in 2006 stressed that the United States passed an act regarding person with disability employment also known as Americans with Disability Act (ADA, 1992) aimed to provide employment opportunities for the truly disabled people where in the absence of legislation are unable to find employment. An article of Philstar (Philippine Star Newspaper) in its September 22, 2012 issue quoted assistant marketing manager of Sarrosa International Hotel and Residential Suites, Hendrik Ryan that "just because handicapped people are disabled doesn't mean they cannot do anything in the hotel industry". He envisioned the hotel to be a PWD-friendly and the first hotel in the global industry that has PWD's as staff.

Given such backdrop of PWD's employment issue, this research answers the question, what are the requirements a person with disability should possess in order for them to acquire a job. It intends to find out organizations like retail, food establishments, government agencies and local government units who recognize abilities of PDW's as potential employees.

Employing persons with disability is a challenge to companies. Inherent limitations among PWD's, tempted

management to think it as a burden and some hire them with reservations.

The low rate of employment among PDW's despite of their disabilities to perform a certain job with efficiency prompted the researchers to probe what specific skills may be required for a PWD's to be at par with employees with no special needs.

II. METHODOLOGY

Respondents

This undertaking utilized descriptive method of research using quantitative approach. The City of Calamba in the province of Laguna is the local of the study. There were two groups of respondent-institutions who are currently employing persons with disabilities (PWD's) and are willing to hire PDW's in their workforce. The first group were managers and human resource officers of private enterprises. One engaged in retail of about two thousand employees and three popular food service chains. The second group were composed of department heads (Managers) and personnel officers of three government agencies and a local government unit.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a self-made questionnaire mainly adopted from the ideas of Robert Katz (1955), particularly on the hard skills that may be required for employability of disabled person. Questions on cognitive abilities and dynamicity of skills were based on Kurt Fischer and Zheng Yan (1980), Items were designed and developed to determine the requirements, educational attainment, acceptable age and sex and kinds of disability in hiring PWD. These instrument were content-validated and pilot-tested among fifteen volunteer-respondents from private enterprises and government agencies using 5-Point Scale.

Gathering and Analysis of Data

About ninety-six percent (96%) of the prospective respondents participated in the study. Business' human resource officers and those who are in managerial and supervisory positions. After two days, the researchers retrieved the questionnaires and contacted them if there would be any additional questions or concerns regarding the survey.

Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used in the analysis of data. Frequency Distribution and Percentage were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents. The weighted mean was used to determine the preferred disability, educational attainment, acceptable age and sex in

hiring person with disabilities. Analysis of Variance was used to test the significant difference on the requirements in hiring person with disabilities as perceived by the business managers,

human resource officers and supervisors of selected retail, food establishments, government agencies and a local government unit.

Operational Framework

Figure 1

Description of the Respondents

TABLE 1.0 Demographic Profile

Age	HR Officers		Manager/Supervisor	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
24 – 31 years old	5	62.5	12	24.5
32 – 39 years old	1	12.5	9	18.4
40 – 47 years old	1	12.5	7	14.3
48 – 55 years old	0	0	8	16.3
56 – 63 years old	1	12.5	7	14.3
No answer	0	0	6	12.2
TOTAL	8	100.0	49	100.0
Sex				
Male	4	50.0	22	44.9
Female	4	50.0	27	55.1
TOTAL	8	100.0	49	100.0
Educational Attainment				
(Vocational)	0	0	2	4.1
College Graduate	6	75.0	34	69.4
Graduate Studies	2	25.0	13	26.5
TOTAL	8	100.00	49	100.0

Majority of the respondents were Human Resource Officers, sixty two point five percent (62.5%) and relatively young between twenty-four to thirty-one age brackets. Eighteen point four percent (18.4%) Managerial and Supervisorial Positions belonged to middle age (40-47) and the rests were veterans. Majority and younger respondents were from the managerial and supervisory levels. The oldest was sixty one from the Managerial position. Seventy five percent (75%) and twenty five percent (25%) are college graduates and have attended graduate studies respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Employers generally prefer PWD’s with variety of soft or human skills like team work, problem-solving, Communication, and decision-making. Hard skills especially ability to draft plans, data analysis and computer applications are considered priority requirements for PWD’s by human resource officers, managers and supervisors. Mathematical abilities would surely be a competitive advantage.

TABLE 2.0 Required Skills

Indicators	Human Resource Officers		Manager / Supervisor	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Communication skills	4.38	Highly	4.47	Highly
2. Decision making	4.38	Highly	4.22	Highly
3. Leadership skills	3.88	Required	4.22	Highly
4. Team-work	4.75	Highly	4.53	Highly
5. Problem solving skills	4.50	Highly	4.12	Required
Composite Mean	4.38	Highly	4.31	Highly
Hard Skills				
1. Computer applications	4.14	Required	4.06	Required
2. Data analysis for application	4.20	Highly	4.04	Required
3. Working Linguistics skills	3.25	Required	3.37	Required
4. Ability to draft plan	4.25	Highly Required	3.63	Required
5. Mathematics skills	4.00	Required	3.61	Required
Composite Mean	3.97	Required	3.74	Required

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79: Not Required
 1.80 - 2.59: Less Required
 2.60 - 3.3: Moderately Required
 3.40 - 4.19: Required
 4.20 - 5.00, Highly Required

TABLE 3.0 Preferred Educational Attainment

Indicators	Human Resource Officers		Manager / Supervisor	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Elementary Graduate	3.00	Moderately	3.18	Moderately
2. High School Graduate	3.50	Required	3.55	Required
3. Vocational Graduate	3.25	Moderately	3.55	Required
4. College Undergraduate	3.75	Required	3.73	Required
5. College Graduate	4.13	Required	4.20	Highly
6. Post Graduate Studies	3.00	Moderately	3.05	Moderately
Composite Mean	3.44	Required	3.54	Required

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79: Not Required
 1.80 - 2.59: Less Required
 2.60 - 3.39: Moderately Required
 3.40 - 4.19: Required
 4.20 - 5.00: Highly Required

A certain level of educational attainment is a basic requirement for employment as the state gives equal access to education in accordance to Section 12 of the Article 7277, of the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons. Private and public agencies prefer college graduates although at least high school

graduates may be considered. Graduate studies surely boost employability.

TABLE 4.0 Preferred Age and Sex

Age	Human Resource Officers		Manager/Supervisor	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Between 18-27	4.38	Highly Preferred	4.16	Preferred
2. Between 28-37	3.88	Preferred	3.69	Preferred
3. Between 38-47	2.63	Moderately	3.20	Moderately
4. Between 48-57	1.75	Not Preferred	2.49	Less Preferred
5. 58 and above	1.63	Not Preferred	2.00	Less Preferred
Mean	2.85	Moderately	3.11	Moderately
Sex				
1. Male	4.25	Highly Preferred	3.67	Preferred
2. Female	4.13	Preferred	3.71	Preferred
Mean	4.19	Preferred	3.69	Preferred

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79: Not Preferred
 1.80 - 2.59: Less Preferred
 2.60 - 3.39: Moderately Preferred
 3.40 - 4.19: Preferred
 4.20 - 5.00: Highly Preferred

Human Resource Officers, Managers and Supervisors showed preference for younger workforce of PWD's, sex was secondary. Despite preference of Human Resource officers to employ male PWD's, Managers and Supervisors apparently do not give much emphasis on the sex. Philippine Statistics Authority Report (Erica, 2003) Sex disability ratio: 104 males with for every 100 females.

TABLE 5.0 Disabilities that are Considered Employment

Indicators	HR		Manager/Supervisor	
	WM	Interpretation	WM	Interpretation
1. Amputated limbs	2.75	Moderately	2.84	Moderately
2. Walking disability	3.13	Moderately	2.88	Moderately
3. Strapped on wheelchair	2.63	Moderately	2.63	Moderately
4. Partial Blindness	2.75	Moderately	2.78	Moderately
5. Deaf person	2.50	Less	2.29	Less
6. Mute person	2.50	Less	2.29	Less
7. Deaf and mute person	2.50	Less	2.10	Less
8. Any disability	2.75	Moderately	2.55	Less
Mean	2.69	Moderately	2.55	Considered

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79: Not Considered
 1.80 - 2.59: Less Considered
 2.60 - 3.39: Moderately Considered
 3.40 - 4.19: Considered
 4.20 - 5.00: Highly Considered

There is general reluctance of Human Resource Officers, Managers and Supervisors in hiring persons with disabilities. Only disabilities that do not directly affect work processes are considered employable. Some employers still see disabilities like being mute and deaf as hindrances for productive employment. It appears that government efforts and laws are not suffice in providing employment as income-generating for person with disability as articulated. (Mina, 2010)

TABLE 6.0 Significant difference between soft and hard skills on hiring PWD's

Variables	T-test Computed Value	T-test Critical Value	Interpretation	Decision
Soft Skills & Hard Skills	2.781	2.306	Significant	Reject Null Hypothesis

Employers give due consideration on what skills prospective PWD-Employee possesses. Retail stores and food establishments requires more of soft skills including communication and teamwork. Government agencies and units require more of hard skills such as computer skills, planning skills and data analysis.

TABLE 7.0 Problems Encountered in Hiring PWD's

Indicators	WM	Interpretation	Rank
1. Behavioural	3.50	Serious	1
2. Negative Attitudes	2.88	Moderately Serious	4
3. Lack of Self-esteem	3.25	Moderately Serious	2.5
4. Acceptance of Colleagues	2.75	Moderately Serious	5.5
5. Bullying of Colleagues	2.75	Moderately Serious	5.5
6. Discrimination	3.25	Moderately Serious	2.5
Composite Mean	3.06	Moderately Serious	

Legend: 1.00 - 1.79: Not Serious
 1.80 - 2.59: Less Serious
 2.60 - 3.39: Moderately Serious
 3.40 - 4.19: Serious
 4.20 - 5.00: Highly Serious

There is serious behavioural problems encountered by Human Resource Officers who initially make decisions in hiring persons with disability. Lack of Self-esteem and Negative Attitudes compounded by Discrimination and Possible Bullying of Colleagues aggravates the problem. This is a manifestation to the statement of the United Nations Enable (2007) that PWD's are frequently not considered potential employees due to myth and prejudice that continue to limit understanding and acceptance of disability as averred in Karen Markel, *et al.* (2009) that typical problem face by the PWDs is stereotyping. Some employers and employees alike think that they have diminished capacity and Apama Dass, (2014) further attested that they may need more resources to achieve the same outcomes compared to non-disabled persons.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

1. Employers prefer male and younger PWD's workforce, below thirty years of age.
2. Soft skills are preferred over hard skills particularly articulate communications and ability to work as at team.
3. Hard skills are also required like ability to analyze data for practical computer applications
4. There are restrictions on the hiring of PWD's: walking disability, amputated limbs and with visual impairment or Partial Blindness are considered for employable.
5. A PWD with a college has high employability. High school graduates with vocational training may be considered.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Persons with Disabilities should develop practicable soft and applicable hard skills at a very young age.
2. Government agencies mandated by law to monitor employability of persons with disabilities should ensure that their employment is primarily based on skills.
3. Government and private educational institutions should create special curriculum and training programs especially on desirable attitudes for Persons with Disabilities.

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